

interview transcript (Business strategy)

Interviewer: AA

Interviewee: JA Head of USA Operations

Interview Setting: Interview conducted in office of Headquarter company in the USA building. The interview was conducted at 3:30 PM on Wednesday afternoon.

Affiliation with interviewee: Senior executives operations of Brooks Sports USA

(Summary draft of Interview)

Interviewer : *Product Approval Committee (PAC) – Membership, Charter, and Roles & Responsibilities*

Interviewee : Need to clear get company year target plan for both department team follow up

- 1) Introduction – PAC Charter, Roles and Responsibilities (JA)
- 2) Integrated Spring Line Margin Review (JB)
- 3) Style-by-Style Project Reviews (PC)
- 4) Production / Capacity Planning and Intro Dates Discussion (AA)

Interviewer : Makes a clear decision on each product in the line ?

“Go” if all business objectives can be met and adequate risk management plans are in place

“Redirect” if project gaps can be remedied with confidence—establish a time to confirm that gaps have been closed

“No-Go” if project gaps cannot be remedied—project is cancelled outright or deferred to a future line

Interviewee : On short time-line its really necessary set up and quick make decision for operation / manufacture.

Interviewer : Sports footwear Professional distribution network, agent loyalty and market share ?

Interviewee : The future of the industry is digital. The specialization of the people involved in all the distribution channels is crucial in reducing errors and getting a better understanding of the product.

It is also an opportunity for online distributors to show all their attributes for better distribution and increase loyalty and market share.

Interviewer : Customer Loyalty, Brand Awareness and After-sales Service Network ?

Interviewee : The after-sales service definition is the set of actions you take to follow up with your customers after they've made a purchase. After-sales service and customer satisfaction are closely linked. The aim of after-sales service is to keep your customers happy and engaged with your brand. This could mean checking in with your customer and asking for feedback, having reliable customer support options and providing high-quality how-to guides. a new learning platform could provide excellent after-sales service by sending a personalized follow-up email to see how setup is going.

They could offer a demo walkthrough or use automated solutions to help customers get started. There are many ways to deliver after-sales service, meaning support extends beyond the sales team. Service after the sale can be provided by the retailer, manufacturer, customer service, chatbot or a training provider. It's often included as part of the overarching marketing strategy. The key reason that most businesses focus on after-sales support is that it increases brand loyalty and customer retention.

Interviewer : How to increase your customer loyalty ?

Interviewee : Happy, loyal customers spend more and buy products more often than new customers. If you treat your existing customers well, they'll choose you over other companies when they're next looking to make a purchase. The less happy your customers feel with their after-sales service, the more likely your customers are to try a competitor the next time they make a purchase.

The goal of after-sales service is to maintain communication with your customer and keep them engaged with your brand. You can do this in several ways, including:

A regular email newsletter , Personalized emails for key dates and anniversaries

Relevant information such as articles, videos, guides and webinars that advertise new products or help them to make the most of things they've already purchased

By sending personalized content, you add value to their customer experience. Further, because you're showing your expertise and providing them with all of the information they need, they are far less likely to leave your company for a competitor.

Interviewer : Reduce the waste of earth resources and fulfill a corporate social responsibility

Interviewee: For companies committed to CSR, it's important for businesses to engage in environmentally friendly practices. Corporations can be significant contributors to greenhouse gas emissions, pollution, waste, and natural resource depletion—but by committing to environmental responsibility, a business takes ownership over its impact on the environment.

Depending on a business's size and industry, environmental responsibility can take many different forms. For some companies, it means using alternative energy sources and sustainable materials. For others, it means enacting a company-wide recycling program or donating to and volunteering for local environment-focused organizations.

Special technical treatment of waste and chemical substances, the impact of products on the environment, reducing the waste of earth resources, and fulfilling corporate social responsibility.

Interviewer: Thanks for your time.

Interviewee: You are welcome.